

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

RABEP1

(RAB GTPase Binding Effector Protein 1)

A Target Enabling Package (TEP)

Gene ID / UniProt ID / EC	9135 / Q15276
Target Nominator	TREAT-AD
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Therapeutic Area(s)	Alzheimer's disease
Document version	1.0
Document version date	January
Citation	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14594607
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CONTENTS OF TEP

Bioinformatic target analysis: Target Source & Hypothesis

Protein constructs & expression methods: RABEP1A-c019. Protein expression in insect cells. Entire CDS, M1-T862. Codon optimised.

TARGET SOURCE & HYPOTHESIS

Why was the target selected? This target was identified through a protein quantitative trait locus analysis.

TREAT-AD Target Risk Score: 3.4 (rank #2477, 90th percentile)

The TREAT-AD Center has developed a target ranking score encompassing genomics and genetics evidence. The Target Risk Score represents the gene target's general relevance to Alzheimer's Disease, and is the sum of the target's Genetics Score and Genomics Score. Target Risk Score values range from 0 to 5, with 5 being evidence of the strongest association with AD. A complete description of the methodology used to calculate these scores is available [here](#). This score was taken from Agora, Data Version syn13363290-v62.

The TREAT-AD Target Risk Score for this target is 3.4 out of 5 (rank #2477, 90th percentile). The individual score components include 2.19 of 3 for genetics, and 1.21 out of 2 for genomics. The meta-analysis of proteomic and transcriptomic data sources used in the genomics score indicates that the expression of RABEP1 protein is significantly decreased in brains from patients with AD.

The TREAT-AD Center has also developed a target categorization system specific to AD relevant processes, termed biological domains (biodomains). These biological domains are defined by constituent Gene Ontology (GO) terms and genes are then annotated to specific biological domains via GO term annotations. RABEP1 is annotated to GO terms primarily from the Endolysosome, Proteostasis, and Apoptosis biological domains.

Overall	rank	pct	GeneticsScore	OmicScore
3.4	2477	90.07	2.189	1.211

Cell-type specific expression is assessed using single-cell expression data from the Seattle Alzheimer's Disease Brain Cell Atlas (SEA-AD). The distribution of expression values for all genes found in each broad cell type are displayed as violins. The expression of the target in subtypes within each broad class is shown as a point. Blue points show the summary expression of cells from individuals with no dementia, while red points show summary metrics of cells from dementia patients. Open circles reflect low

confidence measures of expression. The expression of RABEP1 is confidently detected in all cell types within this dataset.

SUMMARY OF PROJECT

RABEP1 is a Rab GTPase activating protein that scores well for AD risk and is involved in both secretory and endosomal vesicle trafficking (see next section). The connection with AD is unknown, but likely involve changes in intracellular vesicle trafficking or autophagy, as RABEP1 has roles in both areas of cellular homeostasis(1). The goal of this project is to provide a basic target enabling package (TEP) composed of purified protein, 3D protein structural analysis, bioinformatics analysis and identified and characterized antibodies. These resources will hopefully facilitate greater investigation into the connections between RABEP1 and Alzheimer's disease by the scientific community.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

RAB GTPase Binding Effector Protein 1 (RABEP1) is involved in the regulation of endocytosis through direct association with Rab4, Rab5 and members of the adaptin family(1, 2). RABEP1 stimulates the activation of Rab4 and Rab5 through RabGEF5, promoting conversion of GDP to GTP binding, activating the small G-protein endocytic factor(1-3). RABEP1 facilitates intracellular compartment shifts from the ER to the Golgi complex, and localization of some core channels to the cilia(4, 5). The trafficking through the ER/Golgi complexes may be mediate through associations with GGA1, which interacts with RABEP1(6, 7). The endocytosis of numerous proteins is also regulated by RABEP1, notably including the EGFR receptor within the CNS(8, 9). RABEP1 (also known as rabaptin-5) cleavage during apoptosis may promote the changes in cytological structure of the cell, and advance apoptotic progression(10, 11). The mechanistic interaction with AD is unknown, and likely involves its role within the early endosome and the recycling endosome pathways(12-15), as numerous studies have shown these biological processes to be deleteriously impacted in AD. The goal of this project is to provide additional resources to facilitate the investigation into the precise nature and role of RABEP1 in disease pathogenesis.

RESULTS – THE TEP

Proteins Purified

1. RABEP1A-c019. Protein expression in insect cells. Entire CDS, M1-T862. Codon optimised.

See **Additional information (section 1)** with details of plasmid expression constructs and purification procedures.

CONCLUSION

The tools presented here provide a foundation for further biological investigation of the role of RABEP1 in AD.

FUNDING INFORMATION

The work performed by the Emory-Sage-SGC-JAX TREAT-AD Center has been funded by the National Institute on Aging through grant U54 AG065187.

Materials and Methods

Proteins Expression and Purification

All relevant plasmids are available on addgene: [TREAT-AD plasmid collection](#)

References

1. Millarte V, Spiess M. RABEP1/Rabaptin5: a link between autophagy and early endosome homeostasis. *Autophagy*. 2022;18(3):698-9.
2. Vitale G, Rybin V, Christoforidis S, Thornqvist P, McCaffrey M, Stenmark H, et al. Distinct Rab-binding domains mediate the interaction of Rabaptin-5 with GTP-bound Rab4 and Rab5. *Embo j*. 1998;17(7):1941-51.
3. Gournier H, Stenmark H, Rybin V, Lippé R, Zerial M. Two distinct effectors of the small GTPase Rab5 cooperate in endocytic membrane fusion. *Embo j*. 1998;17(7):1930-40.
4. Kim H, Xu H, Yao Q, Li W, Huang Q, Outeda P, et al. Ciliary membrane proteins traffic through the Golgi via a Rabep1/GGA1/Arl3-dependent mechanism. *Nat Commun*. 2014;5:5482.
5. Valsdottir R, Hashimoto H, Ashman K, Koda T, Storrie B, Nilsson T. Identification of rabaptin-5, rabex-5, and GM130 as putative effectors of rab33b, a regulator of retrograde traffic between the Golgi apparatus and ER. *FEBS Lett*. 2001;508(2):201-9.
6. Zhu G, Zhai P, Wakeham N, He X, Zhang XC. Analysis of the interaction between GGA1 GAT domain and Rabaptin-5. *Methods Enzymol*. 2005;403:583-92.
7. Zhai P, He X, Liu J, Wakeham N, Zhu G, Li G, et al. The interaction of the human GGA1 GAT domain with rabaptin-5 is mediated by residues on its three-helix bundle. *Biochemistry*. 2003;42(47):13901-8.
8. Parkinson G, Roboti P, Zhang L, Taylor S, Woodman P. His domain protein tyrosine phosphatase and Rabaptin-5 couple endo-lysosomal sorting of EGFR with endosomal maturation. *J Cell Sci*. 2021;134(21).
9. Park MH, Choi KY, Min do S. The pleckstrin homology domain of phospholipase D1 accelerates EGFR endocytosis by increasing the expression of the Rab5 effector, rabaptin-5. *Exp Mol Med*. 2015;47(12):e200.
10. Swanton E, Bishop N, Woodman P. Human rabaptin-5 is selectively cleaved by caspase-3 during apoptosis. *J Biol Chem*. 1999;274(53):37583-90.
11. Cosulich SC, Horiuchi H, Zerial M, Clarke PR, Woodman PG. Cleavage of rabaptin-5 blocks endosome fusion during apoptosis. *Embo j*. 1997;16(20):6182-91.
12. Christoforides C, Rainero E, Brown KK, Norman JC, Toker A. PKD controls $\alpha\beta3$ integrin recycling and tumor cell invasive migration through its substrate Rabaptin-5. *Dev Cell*. 2012;23(3):560-72.
13. Popa I, Deneka M, van der Sluijs P. Expression and properties of the Rab4, Rabaptin-5 α , AP-1 complex in endosomal recycling. *Methods Enzymol*. 2005;403:526-40.
14. Pagano A, Crottet P, Prescianotto-Baschong C, Spiess M. In vitro formation of recycling vesicles from endosomes requires adaptor protein-1/clathrin and is regulated by rab4 and the connector rabaptin-5. *Mol Biol Cell*. 2004;15(11):4990-5000.
15. Deneka M, Neeft M, Popa I, van Oort M, Sprong H, Oorschot V, et al. Rabaptin-5 α /rabaptin-4 serves as a linker between rab4 and gamma(1)-adaptin in membrane recycling from endosomes. *Embo j*. 2003;22(11):2645-57.

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